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D18.2

Outreach Strategy Report

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report is a deliverable of Task 18.2 dedicated to the outreach to the industrial community as part of WP18 "Bridging academic and industrial research". This report proposes a marketing plan to raise awareness on the industrial community.

It will cover the following topics:

- THE INDUSTRIAL ENGAGEMENT OF NFFA EUROPE
- THE INDUSTRIAL ENGAGEMENT GOALS AND THE TARGET AUDIENCES
- AN ONLINE MARKETING PLAN INCLUDING THE COMMUNICATION CHANNELS AND THE EDITORIAL BOARD
- AN OFFLINE MARKETING PLAN INCLUDING A SHORTLIST OF EVENTS TO ATTEND, THE LIST OF SUPPORTING MARKETING MATERIALS TO CREATE
- THE INDUSTRIAL CONTACT OFFICE NETWORK (ICONET) CONTRIBUTION TO SUPPORT THE SCHEDULED OUTREACH CAMPAIGN AND TO ASSIST COMPANIES IN DRAFTING AND PRE-ASSESSING HIGH-QUALITY PROPOSALS

2 PREMISE

2.1 Industrial engagement of NFFA Europe

The PILOT project builds on the success of the NFFA-Europe INFRAIA-1-2014-2015 actions. During the NFFA-Europe project (2015 - 2021) 495 proposals have been submitted through 15 calls. During the campaign, 321 proposals were accepted with an acceptance rate of 65%. The number of accepted industrial proposals has reached 11.5%. This number is higher than the objective initially set at 5%. A linear correlation has been observed between the number of total projects and the number of industrial projects. This number is in line, or even higher to the quota that is usually declared by scientific RIs much more mature than NFFA. However, the industrial involvement includes not only entities that access directly such as SMEs and large companies but also academics through Private Public Partnerships (PPPs) or other types of collaborations. Industrial direct access is the most impactful for the NFFA industrial program, as a consequence, it will be the main focus and goal for the outreach campaign. An investigation has been carried out to identify and quantify proposals with direct access. For NFFA Europe, direct access account for 5.3% of all accepted proposals with an acceptance rate of 57% (17 proposals submitted over 30 proposals submitted).

	# submitted	# accepted	Acceptance rate
Overall	495	321	65%
Industrial	59 (11.9%)	37 (11.5%)	63%
Direct industrial entities	30 (6.1%)	17 (5.3%)	57%

2.2 Objectives of NEP industrial programme

The main goal of NFFA-Europe-Pilot (NEP) is to enhance European competitiveness in nanoscience and nano-to-micro analysis and nanotechnology. The uniqueness of NEP is to offer, to a broad academic user community and industry/SMEs, combined access to the most advanced research tools for nanoscience and nano-to-micro analysis available in Europe. For NEP campaign (2021-2026), 16 quarterly calls are scheduled over 5 years (accounting for the access deferral periods needed at the beginning and the end of the project). During the first 2 calls, a total of 89 proposals have been submitted and 55 of them have been accepted. 5 proposals have an industry involvement which represents 9% which is below the one reached during NFFA Europe (12%) but above the KPI fixed in the NEP proposal (7%) considering the consortium has raised its ambition compared to NFFA EUROPE (5%).

	# Submitted	# Accepted	Acceptance rate
Overall	89	55	62%
Industrial	10 (11.2%)	5 (9.1%)	50%
Direct industrial entities	2 (2.2%)	0 (0%)	0%

For NEP, 2 industrial proposals have been submitted through direct access and 0 have been accepted (0% of all proposals). These values are well below those obtained with NFFA Europe (5.3%). One of the main ambitions of this outreach strategy is to raise the direct industry involvement at a 5% minimum.

By considering the capacity of the NFFA with approximately 5000 Unit of Access (UoA), the number of projects over the 5 years is expected to be around 420. To fulfill the 7% industry engagement, the estimated number of industrial projects accepted has to be 29 and the estimated number of submitted proposals has to be at least 46 with a rate of acceptance of 63% (NFFA-Europe). It means, at least 3 industrial proposals have to be submitted at each call or 12 by year (4 calls). So far, it has been achieved with 9% industry involvement and it is likely the KPI goals (7%) will be respected without any further actions from the dedicated business developer. However, direct access is extremely low with 0 proposals accepted. The expected impact of the outreach strategy presented in this report is to raise this figure to 5% which was the case in NFFA Europe. In order to fulfill this objective, for the forthcoming years, 21 proposals have to be accepted which led to 37 proposals submitted by considering an acceptance rate of 57% (NFFA Europe). By assuming a transformation rate of 10% (1 proposal submitted for 10 companies contacted), we need to contact at least 370 companies in order to get a 5% direct SMEs/industry access. The business development campaign will start in April 2022 (M14) and will end 2 months before the end of the contract of the dedicated business developer (M44). It gives us a campaign of 31 months which results in an average objective of 12 companies reached every month with an average expected impact of 3 proposals submitted and 2 proposals accepted through direct access for each call.

2.3 Target audiences

The ambition of NEP for SME/Industrial access is to attract the low TRLs (pre-competitive) research by industry or application-oriented projects.

From the Market analysis report established by INL, a NEP deliverable as part of task 18.1, different strategic audiences have been identified for the outreach campaign. There are two representative cross-sections of the communities that can provide users for NEP facilities, services, and expertise: semiconductors and nanomaterials.

On the one hand, semiconductor companies are well organized into clusters and meta clusters that could act as multipliers. For instance, Silicon Europe Alliance is a meta cluster that unites different clusters all over Europe in Micro- and nanoelectronics industries. INL has also identified national clusters for Semiconductor Industries in the UK, Israel, and Switzerland. These clusters are identified as key targets as they include global players and SMEs that could be in the scope of NFFA target. Strategies will be deployed to approach such networks in the framework of ICONet meetings as part of task 18.4.

On the other hand, companies working in the field of nanoscience are not self-organized in clusters or meta clusters. These companies are a very dispersed group that is hard to target via large clusters, associations, or other collective entities. The reason is the wide range of applications that derives from nanoscience and nanotechnology that makes it difficult for making a cluster of companies. Nonetheless, 4 clusters have been identified that include companies such as SMEs that could be potential prospects or entry points to reach out to industrial players in nanoscience. Nevertheless, reaching out to these types of companies would be as tremendous work as it is required to contact them individually. A preliminary work will be carried out to target specific companies by using bibliography metric tools (e.g. web of science). A preliminary work will be done to identify relevant keywords. A state-of-the-art analysis will be carried out to spot scientific publications in the

nanotechnology domain that includes SMEs, start-ups, or large companies as well as a technological watch by analyzing patents on the open database platform Espacenet. The definition of meaningful keywords will be very important and crucial.

Here are the targets for our outreach campaign

1. Main audience:

SMEs because they have a special need for low-TRL research especially startups in the following core markets:

- Pharmaceuticals / biotechnologies
- Nanomaterials / chemicals
- Nanoelectronics / superconductivity
- Energy

2. Secondary audience

- Big national and international industries looking for precompetitive research and commercial (confidentiality access)
- Professional private intermediary companies such as Scientific Service Companies (SSCs)
- Public and private Contract Research Organization (CROs)

3. Potential partners and other organizations/institutions

- New H2020 strategic partners
- Technological clusters (for semiconductor communities)
- New nodes for NFFA-Europe

4. General audience

The needs of low-TRL research of SME and industry will be carefully addressed and industrial users, as well as academic users, will be encouraged to participate.

3 OUTREACH CAMPAIGN

The **outreach strategy** to the industrial community is presented in the **annex**.

Here is a summary with the major marketing items to be actuated:

Online Communication channels:

- LinkedIn (Posts and discussion groups)
- Youtube (Testimonies)
- Twitter (Posts)
- Facebook (Posts Event-related)
- Website (e.g. website articles)
- Marketing Email (targeted semiconductor and nanomaterials industry communities)

Offline marketing events

- Brokerage events
- B2B meetings

- Visits with industrials

Physical supporting materials

- 3 roll-ups (What, Why and How)
- 1 poster
- 1 powerpoint presentation
- Case study sheets
- Leaflets

4 ICONET

4.1 Presentation and objectives

Among the NEP project, a pilot network of the industrial and commercial offices of the providers (ICONet) will be set up as an ad-hoc solution for facilitating industrial and SME access. Such a network is already in place at most of the member facilities. It will bring a dedicated intermediation service, which will exploit, coordinate and rationalize the competence available in the different Industrial Contact Office (ICOs) often already present at member facilities. This ICOs network (ICONet) will contribute to understanding and translating the needs expressed by the industrial user and identifying the most appropriate technique to answer the need. Furthermore, the ICONet will accompany the industrial users for the access preparation and, when relevant, would help to identify academic partners, among the NFFA user community, to collaborate with the industrial user in order to make the access even more effective.

It will emphasize the connection and the engagement with the industry by exploring a set of tailored communication channels specifically designed via the ICONet.

4.2 Missions

The following tasks are assigned to the ICONet:

- Liaise with ENRIITC (European network of Research Infrastructure and Industry for Collaborations) disseminating the NEP model and opportunities for advanced industrial usage of RI services for low-TRL research.
- Develop pilot services for merit-based selection of industrial projects typically at TRL<3, complementing excellent science criteria (assessed by ARP) with indicators of potential for progress towards higher TRLs, and for socio-economic impact of the expected results.
- Assist the dedicated business developer to provide materials for a specific event (brokerage events, workshops, conferences, networking events, ...)
- Participate directly in an event pertinent for industrial outreach located in the country of the provider to allow the business developer to focus on the different missions of interest.
- Bilateral exchange of entry point contacts/key decision leader for prospects that could be a target for NFFA framework.

- Exchange with professional private companies such SSCs
- Exploit synergies with the INTERREG project CAROTS

In the context of the industrial program, a dedicated business developer will have the responsibility to implement a successful outreach campaign to the industrial community. One of the possible tasks of ICONet is to help the dedicated business developer to achieve the industrial involvement KPI described above. For example, assist him in preparing and printing supporting marketing materials for brokerage events or business meetings the dedicated business developer should attend. The network can also designate a delegate to attend an event that is co-located in the country of the ICO. The ICOs can share bilaterally entry contacts with the dedicated business developer to understand their needs and organize a visit if needed. The objective of ICONet is to work collaboratively in order to increase the visibility and the number of direct industrial access among the industrial community of NFFA. The business developer can also facilitate provide information about a potential prospect to the ICONet so the local delegates can reach on their own to evaluate the R&D need and the possibility to become a NEP user.

It also assists industry and SMEs in drafting high-quality proposals and pre-assess the proposal compliance with the excellence criteria adopted by the NEP system of evaluation. To realize this mission, it will be in contact with TLNet and other experts to understand the feasibility of the proposal inside NFFA framework. ARP will be in contact with ICONet to find suitable complementary experts for particular topics.

It will meet remotely 3 times a year to share good practices and exchange about the current roadmap.

4.3 Implementation

Several actions have been carried out for setting up the ICONet:

- Send an email to every member of the general assembly to ask if they are willing to appoint a delegate of their facilities to be represented on the pilot ICONet (14 members at this day)
- Build a mailing list to share information: nep-iconet@lists.nffa.eu
- Contact every member of the ICONet to organize a virtual kick-off meeting to take place in April 2022 (M14)
- A tentative agenda of this meeting has been established:
 1. Presentation of the outreach strategy
 2. Brainstorming about events attendance and event organization
 3. Discussion about sharing contacts
 4. Design a strategy to attract Intermediary private companies (Scientific Service Companies for instance)

4.4 Professional Private Intermediary Companies

One of the missions of ICONet is exchanging with professional private intermediary companies such as Scientific Service companies (SSCs). Indeed, such types of companies could be a great added value for both NFFA and industrial users. SSCs carry out research and measurement services at (public) research infrastructures on behalf of industrial clients and provide targeted expertise in many technological and scientific fields on a contractual basis.

They could act as intermediaries between potential industrial users and the RIs. A particular focus could be taken at SSCs specialized in measurements and analytical methods, and those specialized in material systems. They could facilitate access for SMEs and large companies that are still reluctant to use RIs because of the apparent complexity of accessing such a framework. SSCs can facilitate the procedures for accessing, making the measurements at RIs, and analyzing the results.

One way SSCs could enter the program is for companies want to access RIs, they can engage with an intermediary. In this case, the intermediary has good knowledge and know-how to use the RI service, both the industrial client and the RI trust the intermediary and there are two contracts concluded (or one tripartite). This kind of access could be implemented for NFFA, where the intermediary submits the proposal, does the experiments and analyzes the data instead of the client.

Although SSCs and RIs share mutual interests they rarely join forces in common international, publicly funded projects. However, if both parties have interest and are the smoothest to develop it could lead to fruitful cooperation. Yet, the number of applications is small, compared to the potential for cooperation. That is why such a cooperation model has to be improved and encouraged by current publicly funded projects large research infrastructures.

Calling out SSCs could bring many added values to both RIs and companies. For the company, they don't need to acquire the expertise and the knowledge outside its core business to define and organize the research. For the RI, the research is done on an area too small or too new to be carried out by TTO/ICO to focus on. SSCs act as a catalytic role for new markets. Moreover, such work develops interactions of SSCs with different clients with the ability to trigger and unveil a strategic positioning by identifying a particular trend shared by several clients. This is an effective way to enhance the long-term relationship between RI and SSC and ensure the production of many future proposals linking RIs and industrial clients.

The different tools (events, contacts sharing, customized outreach strategies) to put in place, for attracting SSCs into NFFA Transnational Access (TA) will be discussed during ICONet meetings and coordinated by DESY.

5 ANNEX

NFFA EUROPE KPIs

	# submitted	# accepted	Acceptance rate
Overall	495	321	0.65
Industrial	59 (11.9%)	37 (11.5%)	0.63
Indirect entities	30 (6%)	17 (5.3%)	0.57

NFFA EUROPE PILOT KPIs: call 1 & 2

	# submitted	# accepted	Acceptance rate
Overall (Goal 420 accepted)	89	55	62%
Industrial (Goal 7% => 30 accepted)	10 (11.2%)	5 (9%)	50%
Indirect entities	2 (2.2%)	0 (0%)	0%

- Increase the number of indirect entities in the proposal submitted (5% minimum)
- Better guide industrial drafting high quality proposal

Ultimate goal:

5% indirect entities on a campaign of 11 calls (Call 4 in June 2022 to call 14 in December 2024)

- For the whole campaign: 21 proposal accepted => 37 proposal submitted => 370 (transformation rate of 10%)
- For a call: ~2 proposal accepted => 3-4 proposal submitted => 30 companies reached

Target audiences

Main audience: need for low TRL research

SMEs/start-ups:

Pharmaceutics / biotechnologies
Nanomaterials / chemicals
Nanoelectronics / superconductivity
Energy

Secondary audience: Precompetitive research and confidentiality access

Large companies
PPPs
CROs

Potential partners: mid/long-term benefit

H2020
Technological clusters
New nodes for NFFA Europe Pilot

General audience

Online Communication Channels

Channels/targets	SMEs + large companies	Potential partners	General audience
LinkedIn (Posts, discussion group)	✓	✓	✗
Facebook (Posts, facebook live)	✓	✓	✓
Twitter	✓	✓	✗
Youtube (Testimonies, success stories)	✓	✓	✓
Email marketing	✓	✗	✗
Website (articles, study cases)	✓	✓	✗

Prospection Plan

Planning and editorial board

Social media	Frequency	Topics
LinkedIn	5 times a month	Usecase pertinent for industry (quarterly market oriented)
		Information about the next call
		Major news about nanotechnology ecosystem (research oriented)
		Major news about SMEs related to the selected market and the nanotechnology
5 per week	once a week	News about events related to industry NFFA is participating
		LinkedIn message
Email marketing	before each events	News related to events
	after each events	Marketing emailing to contacts/leads
	Every 3 month	Industry newsletter
	every month	Targeted and personalized marketing emailing (related to sector of market)
		Contacts found on web of science/linkedin/ official website and so on
Facebook	1 post before each events	Give information we attend this meeting
	1 post during the event	Give practical information (booth number)
		plus short video at the booth to deliver quality content message
	Facebook live during events	
	1 post after	Thank you to visit us at the booth + photo (quality content) + statistics (number of B2B meetings)
	When needed	Post for important messages related to NFFA
Twitter	When needed	Shared post for important news about nanotechnology world
	When needed	Commons and important news
	When needed	Shared post related to industry and nanotech world
YouTube	2 times a year	Success stories Testimonies for NFFA industries
	2 times a year	NFFA short videos for industry at events 2 general one per market
Website Articles	times a year	Success stories/study cases
		News about nanoscience community

Physical Supporting Materials

ICONet implementation

Event Attendance

- Industry Technologies 27 - 29 Jun 2022, Grenoble, France
- Nanoinnovation 20- 23 Sep 2022, Rome - Italy
- Micronora 27 - 30 Sep 2022, Besancon France
- RDV Carnot 12 – 13 Oct 2022 Paris – France
- Techconnect Europe No date set yet
- Photonics Europe 2023
- TechInnov 2023, Paris France
- NanoFis 2023

Outreach actions summary

Highlights	Mars	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec	2023	2024
ICONet meetings												
Online Marketing												
Email marketing												
Prospection (web of science, espacenet, linkedin)												
Success Stories												
Supporting marketing materials												
Powerpoint adapted to industrial community												
Rollups												
Poster												
Case studies												
Other marketing material (brochure)												
Offline marketing												
Industry Technologies												
Nanoinnovation												
Micronora												
RDV Carnot												
TechConnect												
Photonics Europe												
TechInnov												
NanoFIS												